

How futureproof are your file formats?

Final report monitoring obsolete file formats

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Summary

In 2022, the Preservation Watch¹ group of the Dutch Digital Heritage Network had an analysis carried out on the sustainability of obsolete file formats.

The main questions were whether it is possible to predict whether and when a file format will fall into obsolescence, and whether it is possible to determine with which applications a specific version of a file format can be opened. This analysis has led to a series of blog posts² on the KIA platform³ and to this final report.

This final report contains a brief summary of the results of the analysis of a number of datasets, including those from DANS/KNAW and Sound & Vision. It answers the underlying research question: to what extent is a method such as the Bass model⁴ suitable for assessing file formats in an archival context for their growth, peak or decline? Does such a model offer added value compared to simpler methods such as a trend line or simply the naked eye?

The conclusions are twofold. On the one hand, simple graphs of archived file numbers per month or quarter already provide a lot of insight into the aging of certain formats, without the need for simple or complex models. Because even slightly more complex models, such as the Bass model, can have difficulty dealing with large temporal peaks and troughs in the number of archived files.

On the other hand, there is still a lack of additional tools ('tooling') to know whether versions of file formats can still be opened with common software. For many common formats, such as JPEG image standards, this does not quickly pose a risk, but for many table-oriented format versions, such as the Microsoft Access database format, this is already a reality. Currently, no tooling is available that can link such format versions to supporting software versions.

Finally, it is important to mention that for many archives it is still difficult to produce lists of archived files, their exact format versions and the archive date.

¹ <https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/activiteiten/preservation-watch/> (Dutch only)

² The Dutch blogpost:

https://kiacommunity.nl/welcome/search?search%5Bselection%5D=global_thoughts&search%5Btags%5D%5B%5D=reinvantveer The English blogposts appeared on Open Preservation Foundation website: <https://openpreservation.org/author/kiki/>

³ <https://kiacommunity.nl/groups/50-preservation-digitaal-erfgoed/welcome> (Dutch only)

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bass_diffusion_model

Introduction

In July 2022, the Preservation Watch⁵ sub-working group File Formats and Preservation Tools of the Dutch Digital Heritage Network (DDHN)⁶ conducted a request called 'Monitoring obsolete file formats'. This request concerned an analysis of the life cycle of file formats: a quantitative and qualitative study into the predictability of the life expectancy of file formats that are in danger of falling into disuse in the archive sector. The aim of this study was to investigate whether existing analysis models such as the Bass model – a predictive economic model – are useful and reliable in predicting the further decline of obsolete file formats.

Problem definition and scope

Archives are increasingly digital, but this digital world does not stand still. Software and formats that were once widely used (think of WordPerfect, for example) may no longer be so. It is therefore important for the sustainability and accessibility of the data to store them in or transform them into more sustainable or modern file formats. How do we know when a particular file format is in danger of becoming obsolete? Can we gain quantitative insight into when this is the case? For example, can we see the number of files of a particular file format increase or decrease over a certain period of time? In addition to this quantitative main question, we also look qualitatively at aging file formats.

To what extent can it be determined whether a particular variant of a file format can still be

opened with common and available software?

The project on obsolete file formats has also formulated a number of questions that could not be answered:

- In this research, the data from Common Crawl⁷ has not yet been used as a point of comparison between globally used file formats and the local file formats in an archive repository. This is partly due to the limited time period over which Common Crawl collects and makes data available, and because web archives mainly contain web-specific formats that are less common in archive repositories. As a result, the hypothesis cannot yet be sufficiently tested.

⁵ <https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/activiteiten/preservation-watch/> (Dutch only)

⁶ <https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/en/>

⁷ The Common Crawl dataset was designed as an open alternative to the strategies that the major search engines (Google, Bing) use to fill their search indexes. Small parties often do not have the resources to perform a complete scrape of the web. Common Crawl provides this: you can request the text of the part of the internet that can be found and downloaded, in the form of an archive of approximately 100 terabytes.

- Some of the datasets of the participating archives have not yet been analyzed because it proved difficult for some archive institutions to export the metadata and make it available for analysis.
- It is not yet possible to answer the question of how many files in a certain format should at least be present in an archive repository – a threshold value – before action is taken. It appears that no good answer can be given to this yet. Nevertheless, insight into the extent to which the number of copies in a certain file format is decreasing is already of great value.
- Insight into and an overview of the available software with which format versions can be opened is not yet available. It is difficult to determine a threshold value when a specific, less used, format version can still be opened with common software. This includes the GIF format, which has declined significantly in use in recent years, but which can be opened without any problems with many common software. This is a complex aspect that is discussed separately in an appendix to this report.

Publications in the context of this analysis

The assignment was carried out by Rein van 't Veer / Antfield Creations.⁸ As the main implementation of the assignment, five blog posts were written and placed on the Knowledge Network Information and Archive (KIA)⁹ on government information platform Pleio, under the subgroup Knowledge Platform Preservation.¹⁰ The individual blog posts are:

- blog post 1: 'Monitoring Disappearing File Formats 1: Introduction'¹¹ (a plan of action);
- blog post 2: 'File format monitoring 2: the internet as an archive, the Bass model in practice: which internet formats are disappearing?';¹²
- blog post 3: 'Monitoring Disappearing File Formats 3: Sound & Vision';¹³
- blog post 4: 'File format monitoring 4: formats in use at Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)';¹⁴

⁸ <https://reinvantveer.github.io/>

⁹ <https://kiacommunity.nl/welcome> (Dutch only). The English versions of the blogpost appeared on Open Preservation Foundation: <https://openpreservation.org>

¹⁰ <https://kiacommunity.nl/groups/50-preservation-digitaal-erfgoed/welcome> (Dutch only)

¹¹ <https://openpreservation.org/blogs/monitoring-disappearing-file-formats-1/>

¹² Monitoring Disappearing File Formats 2: Common Crawl: The internet as archive, the Bass model in practice: which internet formats are disappearing?

<https://openpreservation.org/blogs/monitoring-disappearing-file-formats-2/>

¹³ <https://openpreservation.org/blogs/monitoring-disappearing-file-formats-3-sound-vision/>

¹⁴ Monitoring Disappearing File Formats 4: DANS

<https://openpreservation.org/blogs/monitoring-disappearing-file-formats-4-dans/>

- blog post 5: 'File format monitoring 5: Applications for disappearing file formats'.¹⁵ This last blog post in this series, episode 5, was published shortly before Christmas 2022.

This final report contains a brief summary of the results of the analysis of a number of datasets, including those from DANS/KNAW and Sound & Vision. It answers the underlying research question: to what extent is a method such as the Bass model¹⁶ suitable for assessing file formats in an archival context for their growth, peak or decline? Does such a model offer added value compared to simpler methods such as a trend line or simply the naked eye?

Structure

The design of this final report largely follows a scientific approach, but is aimed at a broad audience without extensive scientific knowledge in the field of file formats and statistics. The report builds on the previously published KIA blog posts and starts with an introduction that introduces the problem and the main question. Subsequently, the subsequent chapters elaborate on this and offer answers: in chapter 2 we review the most important methods for measuring predictive accuracy, in chapter 3 we discuss the data used to determine the accuracy and in chapter 4 we draw a conclusion.

The report contains two appendices. Appendix 1 contains a technical description of the Bass diffusion model and the way in which the coefficients for it are optimized. Appendix 2 contains a set of recommendations for further research on WikiData. It contains recommendations for improving and supplementing metadata to promote the preservation of outdated file formats.

¹⁵ Monitoring Disappearing File Formats 5: Applications for disappearing file formats
<https://openpreservation.org/blogs/monitoring-disappearing-file-formats-5-applications-for-disappearing-file-formats/>

¹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bass_diffusion_model

Methods

If we want to measure the decline in the use of file formats, we need to apply existing methods or develop new ones. This analysis did not aim to develop new methods, but focused on the usability of a well-known predictive method from econometrics: the Bass model. We discuss the model, previous studies that have been conducted with it, and the method for assessing its reliability.

The Bass model

The Bass model is named after Frank Bass, who published it in 1969 in the article “A New Product Growth for Model Consumer Durables”¹⁷. Bass was looking for a relatively simple mathematical model with which the introduction, rise, boom and bust of the sales of consumer products could be modeled. A technical explanation of the model is included in Appendix 1. In the decades after publication, the model was frequently analyzed and applied. A striking detail is that the original title of the article contained a word order error: the intention was to actually call it “A New Product Growth Model for Consumer Durables”.

The model assumes that consumer product acceptance follows a wave pattern, with a rise, peak and fall.

¹⁷ The article can be read at: https://math.la.asu.edu/~dieter/courses/APM_598/Bass_69.pdf

Image: Example graph of a Bass model, with “influencers” (innovators), “followers” (imitators), which together represent the new adopters.

The Bass model is designed to predict the life cycle of consumer goods in terms of product sales, a combination of the early start by innovators, shown by the dotted line, and the growth and peak sales (somewhat insultingly: imitators, the dashed-broken line) to decline over time.

The ‘innovators’ and ‘imitators’ together form the ‘new adopters’, shown by the solid line (red) in the figure.

Related work

In 2017, Kresimir Duretec and Christoph Becker conducted a study with the Bass model, called “Format Technology Lifecycle Analysis”¹⁸. They conclude that the model provides a reliable methodology to analyze the life cycle of file formats.

Although the authors have done valuable work, there are some problems with the methods of their study:

it uses a manual, visual method of selecting the graph that seems most suitable for a dataset, which makes the result subjective;

no comparison is made with other, simpler methods (so-called baseline methods), such as a linear trend line.

¹⁸ <https://tspace.library.utoronto.ca/handle/1807/75891>

These issues somewhat undermine the conclusions: how do we know whether the method is reliable, if we (potentially) manually move the inflection points in the graph? And how do we know whether the method is accurate, if we have no comparison with another method than the proposed one? This analysis attempts to provide an answer to these knowledge gaps.

Important related work includes the efforts of the National Archives of Great Britain in setting up a register of file formats (PRONOM¹⁹), similar to the Wikimedia initiatives in this direction. The added value of this register cannot be overstated: relying solely on file name extensions such as .PDF and .DOC gives too little information about the exact file format used. Take for example the file format family .DOC, which contains an estimated 18 format versions. Not all formats within this family are still supported by recent software.

Although this in-depth analysis was not possible – the data was simply not available – this analysis is essential for assessing the sustainability of file formats and specific files. We will return to this in detail in the results and appendix 2.

Fitting data in the Bass model

For the analysis carried out in the context of this project, datasets were used (see next chapter) that were attempted to be ‘fitted’ in a Bass model. We will briefly explain how this was done.

A fully automated method was chosen. We cannot expect users to know which knobs (parameters) to turn to obtain better and reproducible results. For a mathematical predictive model, the method must be so objective and unambiguous, and without manual steps, except for the data selection process that is inevitably manual. Moreover, an objective evaluation of accuracy requires an objective, automated process to obtain reproducible results. Based on the open data used in this analysis (although not all data is open) the result is fully reproducible. The source code for the research is published open and reusable as a Python library and script.²⁰

The method for choosing the right parameters for fitting the model was also chosen to ensure as few surprises as possible: the ‘least squares method’. In a number of iterations, the parameters that have the smallest deviation are chosen. The deviation is measured as the square of the distance (d_i) between what the model predicts and where the actual data point is located.

¹⁹ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/>

²⁰ <https://github.com/Antfield-Creations/NDE-monitoring-file-formats>

By ‘sliding’ this regression line, for example, the distance d_i becomes larger and smaller. The least squares method, in the case of the regression line in the example above, searches for the smallest sum of all distances between the line and the data points. This process is fully automated and available in the popular Python function library `scipy`.²¹ Default settings were used where possible to apply this.

Evaluating accuracy

The accuracy of the Bass model is also assessed on the basis of fully automated and common mathematical methods. Here too, we have chosen the simplest possible method: the average deviation (ie in the graph above) of the model from the actual data points.

Comparing accuracy with a baseline model

Based on this average deviation, we can also assess whether the Bass model has added value over other, simpler methods. One such obvious baseline method is a simple linear trend line, also called linear regression. This method is simpler than the Bass model: it has only two parameters (or coefficients) instead of three for the Bass model and is computationally much simpler. In order to determine whether it is worthwhile to use a more complex model such as the Bass model as an analysis method than a simpler model, it is therefore necessary that the Bass model performs better than the baseline method.

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https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/generated/scipy.optimize.least_squares.html#scipy.optimize.least_squares

A linear regression line, as mentioned, has two coefficients: the slope of the line, or the slope coefficient, and the place where the line crosses the y-axis at the zero point.

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Source: MADe, CC BY-SA 3.0,

<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=1855837>

Data

More than a methodological study, the aim of the analysis was to become more familiar with the metadata of various parties in the Digital Heritage Network, as well as to analyse data from similar but different sources. The how and why of this is explained in detail.

The analysed datasets are:

- Common Crawl data;
- file metadata from DANS/KNAW;
- file metadata from Beeld & Geluid;
- file metadata from the KB.

We briefly explain each dataset.

Common Crawl

The Common Crawl dataset was designed as an open alternative to the strategies that large search engines such as Google and Bing use to fill their search indexes. Small parties often do not have the resources to scrape the entire web. That is why Common Crawl offers a solution: you can request the text of parts of the internet that are available and can be downloaded, in the form of an archive of approximately 100 terabytes.

The availability of this data is not only useful for building your own search engines, but also for feeding large language models such as ChatGPT, and for performing analyses of the use of file formats on the web. To make this possible, Common Crawl publishes a set of simple counts²² per file format in IANA type (better known as MIME type²³) for each crawl. We used these counts for the first analysis in the series.

The above-mentioned counts are published in a simple csv file of approximately 6000 lines in 320 kilobytes, with each line containing:

- the crawl edition;
- the detected file format;
- the number of counted pages in this format;
- the number of counted links in this format;
- the percentage share (fraction) of the format in the total number of counted pages.

²² https://github.com/commoncrawl/cc-crawl-statistics/blob/master/plots/mimetypes_detected.csv - this file is updated with new statistics for each crawl.

²³ <https://nl.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mediatype>

The main reason for including this Common Crawl dataset in the analysis is to have comparative material for the file formats used in Dutch archives. Are the online file formats used different from those in the archives? Is the progression of formats falling into disuse different online than in the archives?

Image & Sound

As the first dataset in the series of analyses of Dutch archives, we looked at the file formats used in the digital archive of Image & Sound. Image & Sound manages an extensive archive with mainly media, to preserve the heritage of radio and television.

The metadata set of Image & Sound consists of file data from the digitized archive that is available on the public portal²⁴ for private individuals. The combined metadata set itself is not open data and is provided on request by the data service within Image & Sound. The data provided consists of a csv file of over 850 megabytes with almost 5 million lines. Each line contains:

- a link to the 'media suite' in CLARIAH;²⁵
- a category (digital or analogue), the file name;
- the (unpacked) file format;
- a statement whether it is an original digital file (born digital);
- the creation date of the file;
- the first broadcast date;
- the date on which the file was last updated.

An important difference with the Common Crawl dataset is that the data was not supplied aggregated. In the Common Crawl dataset, the counts per file format are per crawl, while the Beeld & Geluid data contains one file (instance) per line, together with the date on which this file was created.

This also explains the difference in size: the file is now more than 2600 times as large. The source metadata of Beeld & Geluid is aggregated into numbers of files per file format, per month. This data is made openly available as a JSON file.²⁶

This aggregated data served as a source for analysing the file formats that are decreasing in number. By only keeping the formats that are decreasing in number, the list became smaller and smaller. This allows us to use linear regression as a validation of the Bass model. The file size has been reduced to 15.4 kilobytes, in 785 lines of 'pretty-printed' JSON, with each period/file number entry and each file format having its

²⁴ <https://zoeken.beeldengeluid.nl>

²⁵ The pages these links refer to are not open and require a login to CLARIAH.

²⁶

https://github.com/Antfield-Creations/NDE-monitoring-file-formats/blob/main/data/nibg/nibg_aggregate_stats.json

own line in the file. The pre-processing of this – converting source metadata to aggregated form – is also openly available.²⁷

DANS

The third analyzed dataset in the series comes from Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), a department of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW). Most of the data from DANS concerns archaeological files as analysis products of excavations and other archaeological (preliminary) research. Archaeologists and other parties are required to supply this data to DANS.

The metadata from DANS is open and can be downloaded via a script. Grateful use has been made of the new archiving system that can supply this additional file metadata. For example, it was decided to select the dates of the files at the moment they were actually delivered, since the metadata of a complete file dataset can already be created before the fieldwork project has started. This allows dataset identification codes to be reserved in advance for inclusion in reports and other communication purposes.

KB

The fourth analyzed dataset concerns that of the National Library of the Netherlands (KB). Although a separate blog post for this analysis has not yet been provided, the KB dataset includes the digitized archive of sources in written, spoken and visual form.

It turned out to be difficult for the KB to produce the source data. The KB metadata set consists of a csv file of over 5 million lines, with a size of 129 Mb, where each line represents an individual file²⁸. The analyzed dataset in aggregated form is summarized in 883 lines of JSON data, with a size of 17 Kb, in which the files are aggregated into numbers of files per period and per file format.²⁹

²⁷ https://github.com/Antfield-Creations/NDE-monitoring-file-formats/blob/main/analysis/nibg_aggregate.py

²⁸ <https://github.com/Antfield-Creations/NDE-monitoring-file-formats/blob/main/data/kb/kbData.csv.gz>

²⁹

https://github.com/Antfield-Creations/NDE-monitoring-file-formats/blob/main/data/kb/kb_aggregate_stats.json

Results

The primary results of the analyses per dataset are included in the separate blog posts, as mentioned in the introduction. In this final report, we want to focus on the broad outlines that emerge from these results and how they contribute to answering the main questions. Detailed information is available in the previously mentioned blog posts.

For the general trends, we focus on the following aspects in this chapter:

- the added value of the Bass diffusion model;
- the developments in the use of older and newer MS Office formats;
- the relationship between software versions and file format versions

Old and new MS Office formats

Many MS Office-related formats have been deposited mainly in the DANS archives. We can distinguish between older and newer format versions based on file name extensions:

- MDB versus ACCDB for MS Access database files;
- XLS versus XLSX for spreadsheets;
- DOC versus DOCX for documents.

The analysis of these shows that it is useful to visualize the trends in the use of these older and newer formats.

Shifts in numbers of older DOC document files (left) versus more modern DOCX (right)

Shifts in numbers of older XLS spreadsheet files (left) versus more modern XLSX (right)

Shifts in numbers of older MDB database files (left) versus more modern ACCDB (right)

For two of these three application areas, the graphs show trends in which the use of older formats is decreasing in favor of newer formats, at least as far as documents and spreadsheets are concerned.

Database files are a notable exception to this trend. The context in which these database files are used is important here. While it is less common to use a 'template' for documents and spreadsheets, this is common practice for Access database files. A template contains a predefined database structure and forms that serve as a standard for collecting data in a database. This offers more guarantees for data integrity, which is more difficult to guarantee with other file formats. An important explanation for the continued popularity of these MDB files lies in the reuse of a standard data structure that has already been entered. In a well-functioning system, changes will not be made quickly and copies in the same file format will be made sooner

The added value of the Bass model

The analyses not only looked at the reliability of the Bass diffusion model, but also at a simpler approach in a regression line, also known as linear regression. The results were mixed overall. There was no clear added value of the Bass model, even in cases where its accuracy was very good.

Let's take a clear example from the Common Crawl dataset – the use of XHTML in web pages. This standard has been falling into disuse for a long time. Although millions of pages are still served in this format, the number of measured pages in the Common Crawl dataset in this format has dropped to about a quarter of the measured peak in the fall of 2017 in 2022. The decrease in absolute numbers shows a nice, slightly curved curve, in which the Bass model clearly makes a better estimate of the latest measurements late 2021/early 2022 than the linear model.

Despite the reliability of the measurements, no graph is actually needed to further support the downward trend in this file format. If archive data is archived in this format, it is evident that this file format – if there is no longer any common software to open and render it directly – needs to be converted to a more common and sustainable file format.

Decreasing trend in XHTML pages in the Common Crawl datasets, from about 1 billion in May 2017 to 400 million in May 2022. Image author, data © Common Crawl.

The trend is also clearly visible in the case of XHTML. Although the Bass model accurately represents the development, the model proves to be redundant because the trend can be recognized at a glance. On the other hand, in situations where the data is too complex for the Bass model, the model adds nothing: the graph does not contribute to understanding an already unclear development. With only three coefficients, the model is not sufficiently expressive here to adequately model the fluctuations in the numbers.

Here is another example, this time from the DANS dataset. The TIFF format experienced a revival in 2010 during a boom period in which a lot of archaeological material was excavated and deposited. In 2018-2019, a new peak became visible, which cannot or does not need to be modeled by the Bass model. The model rightly omits this peak value, but less rightly are the increasing numbers of 2015, 2016 and 2017. These numbers show that the TIFF format is clearly not on its way out, but the Bass model does not provide any additional insight into this situation. The large peak at

the end is not part of the training data, but is used as test data to see whether the increase can be predicted. This peak is therefore not predicted by the model.

File formats, variants and software versions

A second aspect that has been discussed and described in this analysis series concerns the available applications to open disappearing file formats.³⁰ After all, the decision to convert file formats does not only depend on the decrease in use, but also on the availability of common software to open these formats.

Annual numbers of files delivered to DANS 1997-2019, for the file type MDB, based on the production date of the dataset.

Here we have identified a variant of a file format from which we can draw a number of important conclusions. Applications to open the 'Microsoft Database' format (recognisable by the .mdb file name extension) have been in use since 1992. The required 'Microsoft Access' software to open files in these format variants are so common that the database format and the software are often referred to in the same breath as an 'Access database'.

³⁰ <https://openpreservation.org/blogs/monitoring-disappearing-file-formats-4-dans/>

This link between software and file format is beginning to hinder sustainability and accessibility after more than thirty years of development. The current available versions of Microsoft Access software no longer support the early variants of the database files, which means that users of the MDB formats in general – all variants – can no longer count on good support.³¹ This while the number of files supplied to DANS does not yet directly indicate a disappearing file format – in 2019 the highest number of measured files in this format was supplied.

It is unknown which variants of this file format (and in what quantities) are actually supplied. However, in order to be able to undertake the correct preservation action(s), it is important for a heritage organisation to know which version they have in-house. For example: MDB files created in MS Access 97 are still difficult to open with recent versions of MS Access. At the time of writing, of the participating institutions, only the National Archives has – partially – more accurate metadata than just the extension, which is necessary to be able to determine the variant of the format. The tooling for this is present in the software developed by the National Archives of Great Britain: the DROID tool is able to recognise variant Microsoft Access Database file 97 by the signature of the file content.³²

This 97 variant is no longer supported by the current version of Microsoft Access. There are alternative methods to convert files in the Access 97 format, but these require installations of different versions of the Access software to perform this conversion³³.

This means that:

- the file extension .mdb does not indicate which format variant it concerns, since the variant is not part of this extension: the Access 95, Access 97 and Access 2003 variants, among others, share this extension;
- these files can no longer be opened with the current standard software – Microsoft Access as part of the ‘Office Suite’.

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<https://answers.microsoft.com/en-us/msoffice/forum/all/has-microsoft-finally-dropped-support-for-mdb/9aa5d102-3365-4a17-862a-538abda40968>

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<https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/Format/proFormatSearch.aspx?status=detailReport&id=351&strPageToDisplay=signatures>

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https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/convert-a-database-to-the-accdb-file-format-098ddd31-5f84-4e89-8f44-db0cf7c11acd?ranMID=24542&ranEAID=hL3Qp0zRBOc&ranSiteID=hL3Qp0zRBOc-FNJInyZt1A.SCrk9AkAWiA&epi=hL3Qp0zRBOc-FNJInyZt1A.SCrk9AkAWiA&irgwc=1&OCID=AIDcmm549zy227_aff_7593_1243925&tduid=%28ir_axq01kfblokf6hj0yld021qy6v2xdgxniqmyscsp00%29%287593%29%281243925%29%28hL3Qp0zRBOc-FNJInyZt1A.SCrk9AkAWiA%29%28%29&irclickid=_axq01kfblokf6hj0yld021qy6v2xdgxniqmyscsp00

So despite the fact that the files in these MDB formats are still widely in circulation, the conclusion based on their support is that this is a vulnerable format that can be better converted to a more robust equivalent. The MDB format is the main file format that has been identified as high risk in the context of this analysis series. Appendix 2 contains additional recommendations to make the analysis of file formats and available software even more feasible.

Conclusion

Here we evaluate the question to what extent the project 'Monitoring obsolete file formats' has met its objectives.

The primary goal was to assess to what extent the Bass model contributes to monitoring obsolete formats. The conclusion is that the contribution is minimal. In principle, gaining insight into the number of files in exact format versions and when they were archived provides sufficient information for an estimate. However, it is important to note that it can often be difficult enough for digital archive repositories to retrieve this basic information.

The secondary goal was to assess to what extent current tooling is able to determine whether a specific format can still be opened with common applications. Although this is less relevant for commonly used formats such as spreadsheets or documents, it is all the more so for data files that are used for specific information purposes, such as database formats. The conclusion is that there is no reliable source available yet that can make this connection, but that it is possible to create a set of requirements – attached in this report – to work on this problem.

An additional conclusion is that many archives still struggle to provide the necessary information for the analysis of file formats and their prevalence. Nevertheless, two of the four participating archives were able to quickly provide a metadata file or had an open API that could be queried.

Appendix 1: Technical explanation of the Bass (diffusion) model

Frank Bass published the mathematical model named after him in 1969, with the aim of developing a method that could predict the sales development of consumer products. He aimed to design a relatively simple mathematical model that was expressive enough to model the ‘curvature’ of sales.

His model was able to do this, with only a handful of variables. It is also called the Bass diffusion model, but this has little to do with the advanced diffusion models that are currently popular in artificial intelligence, such as Stable Diffusion, and refers to the statistical distribution (diffusion) of the products sold.

In our implementation, however, we use the function that expresses the ‘sales’ s in period t :³⁴

$$s(t) = m \frac{(p + q)^2}{p} \frac{e^{-(p+q)t}}{\left(1 + \frac{q}{p} e^{-(p+q)t}\right)^2} \quad (1),$$

with:³⁵

- $s(t)$ as the number of sales during time period t ;
- between the first square brackets: the number of new users (adopters) during time period t , expressed here as compared to the previous time period;
- between the second square brackets: the market potential for new users;
- the coefficient m : the market potential, or an indication of the potential size of the market;
- the coefficient p : the innovation factor, or the speed at which the product is adopted by early innovators. We could now speak in terms of influencers;
- the coefficient q : the imitation factor, or the speed at which followers purchase the product;

³⁴ As published by Frank Bass in 1969 on page 222, available at https://math.la.asu.edu/~dieter/courses/APM_598/Bass_69.pdf#page=9, see also https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bass_diffusion_model#Model_formulation, elaborated in https://github.com/Antfield-Creations/NDE-monitoring-file-formats/blob/main/models/bass_diffusion.py#L54

³⁵ Sources: <https://www.numberanalytics.com/tutorials/bass-model-new-product-diffusion>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bass_diffusion_model
<https://github.com/NForouzandehmehr/Bass-Diffusion-model-for-short-life-cycle-products-sales-prediction/blob/master/bass.py>, which has been modified to https://github.com/Antfield-Creations/NDE-monitoring-file-formats/blob/main/models/bass_diffusion.py

Based on this formula, it is not necessary to calculate cumulatives: we can work with numbers of files during time period t . This formula has been used to plot the graphs of the file formats that are decreasing in use.

The question is how to determine the coefficients m , p and q of a Bass model. To this end, we apply a number of statistical optimization methods: the coefficients are 'learned' from training data, with 10% of the data – the most recent data points (the last data points in the series) – being used to measure the accuracy of the model and the chosen coefficients.

The chosen optimization algorithm is the least squares method, made available in the widely used Python function library Scikit-learn³⁶. In a number of iterations, the training data is used to bring the Bass model coefficients towards an optimum. In doing so, the squared distance from the model to the actual data points is minimized. The number of iterations is set to 1000 here. In each iteration, the performance of the Bass model for a specific data point is evaluated, after which the coefficients are adjusted to optimize the accuracy (fit) of the model to the actual data points.

³⁶ <https://scikit-learn.org>

Appendix 2: Recommendations for improved durability analysis

Reason

This appendix contains a number of recommendations to better safeguard aging file formats. As emerged from the final report, the moment to take action depends on, among other things:

- the frequency (quantitative) of file formats, and
- the availability of software to open these formats.

This first topic, the quantitative approach, has been discussed in the results of this blog series, with the main conclusion that it is important to gain insight into whether there is an increasing or decreasing trend, rather than using mathematical models to model these trends. Although it is possible to use more complex models with additional coefficients that can better capture the peaks and troughs in trends, the question remains whether this is more useful than a simple estimate of an increasing or decreasing trend. It may also be interesting to investigate whether data for specific file formats from different archive institutions can be combined to observe a common trend or to discover exceptional usage situations.

The second topic, the 'application side', has also been discussed. This shows that there is a need for good data on the usability of certain file formats, with a specific format identified as vulnerable: the 'family' of MDB file formats.

The aim of this appendix is to use this MDB case to arrive at:

- an ideal scenario to arrive at the conclusions that we have now arrived at 'manually';
- a set of practical recommendations to improve the current situation.

Scenario

Many archives can already provide overviews of the number of archived files and the formats used in the form of file extensions. For example, the DANS API can be used to retrieve which files have been archived in MDB format (Microsoft Access or Windows database format). What is often lacking, however, is insight into the 'subformats' or variants of these formats. This information is crucial to determine to what extent a specific variant of the file format is still supported by common software.

Earlier in the report we concluded that the MDB format is now entering a crucial phase: the Access 97 variant of the MDB format is no longer readable in current versions of Microsoft Access. As a result, the readability of these files has become dependent on software that is limited, illegal or perhaps can be installed in a roundabout way. This poses a risk to the usability of these file formats.

In an ideal scenario, an archive can determine which specific files are at risk. Although some of the necessary tools are already available, other essential resources are still lacking. For example, you can use the use case approach of Cockburn (2001)³⁷ to draw up a scenario.

Primary actor

A digitally skilled archivist or curator of an archive institution with digital files.

Prerequisites

- the actor is able to install the software;
- the actor has digital read access to the files in the digital archive.

Step-by-step plan

1. The actor opens the software to perform the file analysis and opens the folder with the files to be analyzed.
2. The software determines the variant of the file format for each file in the selected folder.
3. For each first occurrence of a variant of a file format, the software searches for compatible software to open the file.
4. If a variant no longer has common software to open the file, the software adds the file to a list of vulnerable files.
5. The software shows an overview of the vulnerable file formats and the files that are in this format.
6. The actor creates a new step-by-step plan to convert vulnerable files to a more modern, similar format that is easier to open.

Available scenario components

This scenario is not complex in itself, but can potentially be time-consuming, especially if the archive contains a large number of files. There are possibilities to extend this scenario, for example by caching the metadata of the files, so that they do not have to

³⁷ Writing Effective Use Cases, <https://archive.org/embed/writingeffective00cock>

be analyzed again in a next analysis run. If a file format cannot be identified in step 2, the file should be placed on the list of vulnerable files anyway.

It is also questionable whether it is advisable to distinguish between the 'advertised' format, as indicated in the file extension, and the actually detected file format. This makes it easier to distinguish between TXT files, for example – is it a running text file or a CSV format? This can also help to identify possible errors in the file name extension.

Much of this scenario is already feasible today. Using the DROID³⁸ software, developed by the National Archives of Great Britain in the PRONOM initiative³⁹, it is already possible to accurately determine the file format variant of a file. DROID uses content signatures of a file. For example, a .JPG image file can be recognized by a specific sequence of characters at the beginning of the file.⁴⁰ These signatures have also been published separately, which means that they can also be used in other software.⁴¹

WikiData also includes these file format versions, including those for Access 97⁴², as structured data. This information is available via an open endpoint that can be queried via the internet.⁴³ This makes it easier to keep the software dynamic, although using a SPARQL endpoint can often be difficult for laymen.

Unavailable scenario components

The missing information is in the link between these format versions and software versions, from step 3 in the scenario. Take our case for example, the MDB format in variant Access 97; we then need to know in which software versions it is still possible to open an Access 97 version of an MDB file.

At present, the problem still extends in two directions: the known software versions and the known links between file format versions and software versions.

³⁸

<https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/information-management/manage-information/preserving-digital-records/droid/>

³⁹ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/Default.aspx>

⁴⁰

<https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/Format/proFormatSearch.aspx?status=detailReport&id=667&strPageToDisplay=signature>

⁴¹ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/aboutapps/pronom/droid-signature-files.htm> for all formats, or specific ones such as for MS Access 97: <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/x-fmt/239.xml>

⁴² <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q48005022>

⁴³ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:SPARQL_query_service/Wikidata_Query_Hel

Although limited metadata of some software versions is available in PRONOM, PRONOM only knows software version 2000 of Microsoft Access.⁴⁴ WikiData covers a family of Microsoft Access software⁴⁵, where each version is given as a property, but it lacks entities for each software version that would allow format versions to be related to software versions.

Requirements

In order to meet the relationships between software versions and format versions, adding missing data in WikiData is a suitable starting point. WikiData is curated and well structured, making it suitable as a reliable source to build analysis tools on.

If WikiData were chosen as a source to add this metadata, the following would contribute, among other things:

- A class 'Software Version' or a concept like that. An instance of this class describes a specific version of software, such as Microsoft Access 97.
- A property of this class called 'supported readable format version',⁴⁶ which specifies a relationship to a format version. An instance of 'Software Version' such as Microsoft Access 97 describes this property multiple times: MS Access 97 supports not only the Access 97 format, but also other formats. Finally, it is relevant to mention that many archives still find it difficult to produce lists of archived files, their exact format versions and the archive date.
- A property that describes the closing date⁴⁷ of the release of the software. With the help of this property, it is known whether the software is still being released or not. A condition for this is that a release of the software must be available – not just the source code. Only the availability of source code limits the availability of the software to developers.

Operationalization

In order to meet the above requirements, a reliable inventory source of software versions is first required, which can then be systematically examined. In cases where the software only runs on outdated operating systems, virtualization systems can be used, such as those developed in, for example, the Software Preservation Network⁴⁸ led by Yale University.

⁴⁴ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/Software/proSoftwareSearch.aspx?status=listReport>

⁴⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q80689>

⁴⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P1072>

⁴⁷ Such as <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P582>, <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P2669> or a sub-property of one of these properties.

⁴⁸ <https://www.softwarepreservationnetwork.org/emulation-as-a-service-infrastructure/>

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